

Experience with the accreditation of technical studies in Poland and Thailand's

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Abstract

This article gives an overview of the Poland and Thailand's technical education system with regard to both its quantitative and qualitative scenario and upholds the value of accreditation in quality improvement and quality assurance of educational programmes. The article presents similarities and differences in the treatment of quality through the accreditation and certification procedure for compliance with the requirements of ISO 9001 and the possibility of complementary use of these tools in the process of improving the quality of education in Polish and Thai universities. The following aspects have been considered in the accreditation and certification considerations: comparison of the accreditation procedure, analysis of the mechanism for improving the quality of education in the light of the accreditation and certification procedure, presentation of accreditation standards in the light of process management, the role of stakeholders in improving quality.

Keywords: Accreditation; Quality assurance, Stakeholders.

1 Introduction

Education, like any other activity, is subject to the quality assessment rule for services rendered. The assessment is made by all stakeholders related to this activity (Ulewicz & Blaskova, 2018; Grebski & Grebski, 2019). Although everyone evaluates, the process of assessing the quality of education is not a simple process. First of all, it is difficult to immediately verify the learning outcomes, as these are only possible to be assessed after at least some part of the process has been completed (Lima, Dinis-Carvalho, Flores, & Hattum-Janssen, 2007, Ulewicz, 2014). Even people who are directly subject to the educational process are able to assess it only after some time has passed, often not even immediately after graduation (Koomsap, Ayutthaya, Nitkiewicz, Lima, & Luong, 2019; Padlowska, 2014). A lot of scientific work has been devoted to the definition of quality, and most authors have agreed that a correct and unambiguous definition is impossible. We encounter even greater problems when we want to determine what is the quality of education. It is also believed that the concept of quality cannot be easily adapted to the needs of education (Dabylova, Sroka, & Alibekova, 2020). The uniqueness of the learning process makes it extremely difficult to apply quality assessment procedures known from other areas of human activity, such as production activities (Anttila & Jussila, 2018). Without questioning this statement, however, you can indicate minimum requirements for the quality of the learning process (Wiśniewska-Szałek, Ayutthaya, Mequita & Chattinnawat, 2019; Grebski & Grebski, 2018). This assessment is especially important in the area of a technical education where high mathematical skills are very desired to be able to learn modern data analysis i.a. prediction (Pietraszek, Gadek-Moszczak, & Torunski, 2014; Kot & Ślusarczyk, 2014), fuzzy multiple-comparisons (Pietraszek, Kolomycki, Szczotok, & Dwornicka, 2016), non-parametric modeling (Dwornicka, Radek, Krawczyk, Osocha, & Pobedza, 2017) or development of decision support (Pacana, Pasternak-Malicka, Zawada, & Radon-Cholewa, 2016). It should be remembered that universities create human capital resources necessary to meet the needs of the regional labor market, to take up challenges in the area of R&D or to implement the latest technologies (Jelonek, & Mesjasz-Lech, 2017; Grabara, Hussain & Szajt, 2020)

2 Assessment of education quality

There are many types of university assessment in the literature. The curriculum assessment of the university is well known, which is conducted in relation to fields of study, level and profile of education, and comprehensive assessment, which consists in assessing activities aimed at ensuring the quality of education at the university.

The program and comprehensive evaluation functions in the Polish reality of the higher education system. In the case of program evaluation, the main subject of analysis and evaluation are mainly didactic processes and their learning outcomes related to its specific program (field of study). This assessment also includes selected elements of a comprehensive assessment regarding internal mechanisms for ensuring the quality of education. In the area of higher education was formed four classic models currently used in the evaluation process of the functioning of the university. The presented models can be used both to evaluate the quality of education as well as to the activity of the university. Models are shown in Figure 1. Models of evaluation of the functioning of higher education can be divided into two classes - due to the entity that directly participate in the evaluation (Gates, Augustine, Benjamin, Bikson,, Kaganoff, Levy, Moini, & Zimmer, R 2002, Dura, Moraru, & Isac, 2016). The first type is a group of methods focused on the same university and evaluating various aspects of its operation, while the second focuses attention on students, in an indirect way assessing the work of university as an institution.

Figure 1. Models of evaluation of the functioning of the university

The first model is called self-esteem controlled by an external body and was established on the basis of business solutions. It consists of internal establishing evaluation criteria by the institution which is the subject of an evaluation, and then verifying the fulfilment of these criteria by an external entity. This choice has a chance to succeed regardless of system conditions, but it is preferably suited for systems aimed at improving, of decentralized, with a high degree of heterogeneity. But this is not a model that guarantees the measurability of the work of higher education. This condition is met, on the other hand, by evaluation carried out by an external institution, which, however, does not work in decentralized structures, low-financed. Moreover, such choice may prove to be little effective tool for improving the functioning of academic units. Methods based on gained assessment in the course of teaching students competences perform well in typical decentralized higher education systems. However, these are usually models of "cost-intensive" - associated with the estimation of added value of the teaching process by comparing the achievements "at the entrance" and "exit" from the system. In the literature (Cheng, & Tam, 1997, Ulewicz, Sethanan, Nitkiewicz, & Wiśniewska-Sałek, 2020) are described four methods of quality assurance in higher education:

- Licensing - involves granting university the rights to its functioning. The Licensing unit checks whether the school meets formal requirements.
- Evaluation of the quality - is based on the judgment/certificate about the level of quality of education. The level of quality of education is assessed based on a comparison of achievements of university with specific requirements/standards. When assessing quality of universities the same criteria are determined, taking into account the diversity of the program and forms of education. The evaluation is made by external unit.

- Accreditation - consists in ensuring that the university meets the standards, which guarantee the quality of education. Purpose of this method is to increase confidence in the university and to reduce external oversight.
- Overview - this method involves the review of internal mechanisms to ensure the quality of education at the university and its improvement. This review consists of checking the correctness and effectiveness of the functioning of these mechanisms by external unit.

In the Polish education quality assessment system, quality assessment is combined with accreditation, the possession of which is necessary for conducting educational activities. The presented methods allow for the delivery of solutions to ensure the quality of education at universities, however, they differ among themselves with the boundaries impact on quality. Table 1 provides an overview of the characteristics of quality assurance systems at universities of technology.

Table 1. Features of quality assurance at the university of technology

Systems	Range	Influence on quality	Stakeholder engagement	Objective
Licensing	generally compulsory	little	little	license to operate
Quality assesment	often compulsory	perceptible	little	a comparison of quality, funding
Accreditation	compulsory PKA* other voluntary KAUT**	significant	big	threshold quality assurance
Overview	voluntary	very big	very big	continuous quality improvement

* PKA - Polish Accreditation Commission

** KAUT European Accreditations/Accreditation Commission of Universities of Technology

In Polish conditions of the higher education system, technical universities must be accredited by the Polish Accreditation Commission - this is an obligation arising directly from the Act on Higher Education, Technical universities may voluntarily apply for foreign / industry accreditation, e.g. KAUT. So far, there has not been a situation in Poland that the technical faculty with PKA accreditation did not receive positive KAUT accreditation, nor was the reverse situation noted. KAUT accreditation is included in the environmental accreditation.

In Thailand There are various different kinds of HEIs including (1) designated national research universities receiving special funding and support to be developed into globally competitive universities from the government, (2) open universities which are large public universities having comparatively low admission standards compared to the designated national research universities, (3) the so-called "Rajabhat Universities and Rajamangala Universities of Technology" which are also public universities upgraded from teacher training colleges and Institutes of Technology, respectively, and (4) the publicly controlled universities so-called "autonomous universities" (<https://wenr.wes.org/2018/02/education-in-thailand-2>).

For the assessment of education quality in Thailand, quality assessment is also combined with accreditation. Both public and private universities institutions are required to conduct annual internal quality assurance reviews, which are externally audited by the Higher Education Commission (OHEC) every five years. Generally, the indicators assess input, process, and output/outcome factors. The main components and compulsory indicators for internal assessment are such as: (1) graduate production, (2) research, (3) student development activities, (4) academic services to community, or (5) system and mechanism for quality assurance.

Additionally, a new curriculum offered by the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) is also reviewed the approval processes by the OHEC. The "Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment" (ONESQA), an external quality review agency, is charged with assessing the HEIs' quality assurance mechanisms. However, if institutions decline to improve identified quality problems within a specified period of time, they are subject to closure (<https://wenr.wes.org/2018/02/education-in-thailand-2>).

Table 2. Features of quality assurance of the university Thailand

Systems	Range	Influence on quality	Stakeholder engagement	Objective
- Licensing	- compulsory	- moderate	- moderate	- license to operate
- Quality assesment	- compulsory	- perceptible	- moderate	- a comparison of quality, funding
- Accreditation	- compulsory	- significant	- significant	- threshold quality assurance
- Overview	- compulsory	- significant	- significant	- continuous quality improvement

3 ACCREDITATION

Technical universities in Poland are subject to assessment by the Polish Accreditation Commission or environmental agencies such as KAUP. It is worth looking at what the assessment of the quality of education looks like in Poland. Theoretically, quality management means continuous improvement of the organization. Improvement is a learning process that involves uncertainty and making mistakes. One can put forward the thesis that Polish higher education lacks a holistic approach to quality. This can be demonstrated by the importance attached to details. Unlike ESG, despite continuous positive changes, the PKA quality assessment process is heavily codified and focuses on legality and documentation review. Therefore, PKA still has a purely controlling function, not a perfecting one. After the PKA review procedure was amended, the assessment scale was also changed, currently we only have a positive and negative assessment. Positive assessment is granted for 6 years. In the old four-stage system there was a distinctive, positive, conditional and negative rating. The following scale shall be used to assess the degree of compliance with the specific program evaluation criteria:

- 1) criterion met,
- 2) the criterion met partly,
- 3) criterion not met.

The structure of the program evaluation criterion is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Construction of the program evaluation criterion

Table 3 presents the criteria for the PKA program evaluation in relation to ESG 2015.

Table 3. Criteria for program evaluation PKA (Poland), ESG 2015, and OHEC (Thailand)

Criteria for program evaluation of PKA (Poland)	ESG 2015	OHEC Thailand
1. Design of the study program: concept, learning objectives and learning outcomes	1.1. Policy for quality assurance (reference to quality policy) 1.2. Design and approval of programmes	1. Monitoring Curriculum Standard
2. Implementation of the study program: program content, schedule of the implementation of the study program and forms and organization	1.2. Design and approval of programmes 1.3. Student-centred learning, teaching and assessment	2. Graduates

of classes, teaching methods, apprenticeships, organization of the teaching and learning process		
3. Admission to studies, verification of student achievement of learning outcomes, passing individual semesters and years, and diploma	1.4. Student admission, progression, recognition and certification 1.3. Student-centred learning, teaching and assessment	3. Current Students
4. Competences, experience, qualifications and the number of staff conducting education as well as the development and improvement of staff	1.5. Teaching staff	4. Instructors
5. Infrastructure and educational resources used in the implementation of the study program and their improvement	1.6. Learning resources and student support	5. Curriculum, Teaching and Learning, Learners Evaluation
6. Cooperation with the socio-economic environment in the design, implementation and improvement of the study program and its impact on the development of the field of study		6. Educational Resources Service
7. Conditions and methods of raising the degree of internationalization of the education process in the field of study		
8. Supporting students in learning, social, scientific or professional development and entering the labor market as well as development and improvement of forms of support	1.6. Learning resources and student support	
9. Public access to information on the study program, its implementation conditions and results achieved	1.8. Public Information	
10. Quality policy, design, approval, monitoring, review and improvement of the study program	1.1. Policy for quality assurance 1.2. Design and approval of programmes 1.7. Information management 1.9. On-going monitoring and periodic review of programmes 1.10. Cyclical external quality assurance	

The purpose of KAUT accreditation is:

- assessing the quality of education in the fields of study, in order to determine whether the criteria adopted as the basis for assessment are sufficiently fulfilled to grant accreditation,
- improving the quality of education by making a multi-faceted assessment of study programs and the conditions for their implementation,
- providing reliable information on the quality of education in an accredited course to various stakeholders,
- creating and disseminating high standards of education quality.

The assumptions of KAUT accreditation in relation to PKA accreditation are similar. KAUT places much more emphasis on the impact and participation of external stakeholders as well as on the confirmation and validation of engineering competences and skills. KAUT accreditation is granted for 2 years if the criteria are not fully met or for 5 years. At present, an average of three hundred thousand students study in Poland in over 352 technical faculties reserved at 18 technical universities. Only 70 fields of study have current KAUT accreditation, which accounts for less than 20% of technical fields.

The weakness of these accreditation systems is the lack of qualitative assessment mechanisms for the design of study programs correlated with the graduate's vision on the labor market. Under this area subject assessment should be the key competence of the graduate program. The assessment of intended learning outcomes should include the characteristics of knowledge, skills and competences verified in the form of checked learning outcomes. The evaluation of the program, its content and theirs is also significant matching the learning outcomes assigned to them and maintaining the right balance between the various categories of effects. The weakness of the system is the inability to redefine learning outcomes during the learning cycle - despite the fact that the labor market has redefined its needs. The problem of flexibility in adjusting program content as well as learning outcomes is not easy due to the accreditation and legislative aspects. In areas where we do not have clearly defined criteria, there is a problem with the so-called subjective expert judgment.

For the process to obtain a curriculum approval, in Thailand, there are 3 steps which are (1) Faculty review, (2) university review, and (3) the Higher Education Commission (OHEC) and Office of the Civil Service Commission review (see Figure 3). From Figure 3, in the first stage of review, curriculum development committee deliver the curriculum (both new and existing curriculum) to the faculty committee to review. If the curriculum is met all criteria, then it is screened by the university committee before submitted to the educational council for review. Again, if the curriculum is met all standards, it is approved by the university council. The final stage is the Higher Education Commission (OHEC) and the Office of the Civil Service Commission review. Recognition and recommendation from the OHEC may be required. However, if the curriculum is met all requirements, it is approved by the OHEC and received the letter of degree verification by the Office of the Civil Service Commission.

Figure 3. Curriculum approval procedure of Thailand

4 Conclusion

Measuring the quality of university work is currently one of the key elements in building a positive image and the basis of the accreditation process. The globalization process leading to universal access to educational services, as well as the increase in the number of universities, generates doubts about the quality of educational services they offer. The implementation of monitoring systems and education quality management systems being the basis for consistent action to improve the quality of becomes a certain solution in this regard. In Polish conditions, accreditation is confirmation of meeting the assumed criteria. The weakness of this system is the lack of information on how to improve the quality of education and the degree of additivity of the university to rapid changes related to the requirements of external stakeholders. The Polish Accreditation Commission sees the necessity of changes and introduces comprehensive accreditation, which aim will be to assess the effectiveness of internal education quality assurance systems, with particular emphasis on the role of internal and external stakeholders in the process of quality improvement. Similar activities occur in the case of accreditation in Thailand. However, unlike Poland, the institution controlling the functioning of the education quality assurance system is the Office National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (ONESQA), which is responsible for assessing the university's quality assurance mechanisms. In Poland, the program and comprehensive assessment, which includes the assessment of quality assurance mechanisms, is carried out by the same institution, the Polish Accreditation Commission.

5 References

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